

INVESTIGATING THE INFLUENCE OF INSTAGRAM INFLUENCERS ON YOUTH: A CASE OF LAHORE

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Abstract

This paper was based on a quantitative research study of the influence of Instagram influencers on the youth of Lahore. The research, relying on the Uses and Gratification Theory, aimed to find out the extent to which Instagram influencers could modify the attitude and behaviour of the youth in Lahore. The study employed a quantitative design to assess the relationship between the different variables, as the cross-sectional sampling strategy keyed 308 participants, and stratified random sampling was used to ensure that the selection of a representative was provided in different age groups within the three Lahore universities. The target population consisted of young people between the ages of 18 and 35 above living in Lahore, Pakistan. The data were collected by means of a structured survey questionnaire. The questionnaire held items that evaluated the attitude of the participants toward influencers, the interest in influencer contents, and any behavioural modifications that could be attributed to exposure to the influencers. SPSS played the role of analysing the data which had been collected. Descriptive statistics provided an overview of the responses provided by the survey and demographics of the participants. With the help of inferential statistics such as regression analysis and correlation, relationships between the influencer engagement and behavioural changes among the youth of Lahore were identified. The case study aimed to present empirical information concerning the impact of social media influencers on attitudes and behaviours of young people by conducting a quantitative study of the pressure brought about by Instagram influencers on Lahore young people. This finding has the potential of assisting educationalists, commercialists, and lawmakers to realize the role of influencers in the development of behaviour and culture among youths in the digital era.

INTRODUCTION

Digital revolution of the 21st century has transformed radically the way we share information, communicate and perceive the world. The social media are now very strong tools that have influenced the societal norms and values of the crowd as well as the behaviours and lifestyles of individuals (Castells, 2012; Boyd & Ellison, 2007). Instagram is one of the leading visual storytelling or digital interactions platforms with millions of users all around the world and unique

combination of images, videos, and stories. A new generation of celebrities known as "influencers," who use their significant online presence to interact with audiences and promote goods, lifestyles, and ideologies, have emerged as a result of this visually-driven platform (Abidin, 2016; Djafarova & Trofimenko, 2019).

Youth culture and consumer behaviour are greatly influenced by Instagram influencers, which are people

who have amassed sizable online followings and established credibility in specific niches. These influencers frequently serve as digital role models, and their followers imitate their fashion choices, travel patterns, beauty regimens, and lifestyles (Abidin, 2016). Urban areas like Lahore, the second-largest city in Pakistan and a thriving cultural centre, are particularly affected by this phenomenon. Platforms like Instagram are important socialization and value-formation tools in addition to being entertainment venues, as more than 60% of Pakistan's population is under 30 (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics, 2017).

Popular among Instagram influencers, in general, is the ability to attract and communicate with large numbers of fans, thus possessing much influence over their followers, including youth (Freberg et al., 2011). The evidence indicates that adolescents are at the greatest risk of succumbing to the persuasion of the social media influencers given that, due to their developmental stage, they often seek permission and guidance of these online influencers during their early life (Khan et al., 2021). This dynamic shows that the impact of the influencer culture can be tremendous, particularly in the regions when the young generations might be less likely to engage with old media.

In Lahore, Pakistan, one of the most populated cities where the culture is rich in history and the youths are very vibrant, the influence of Instagram stars is also increasing. The city makes it more interesting to study the relations that exist between social media influencers and the gullible follower. Lahore offers a unique opportunity to investigate how digital influencers shape the lifestyle choices, consumer behaviours, and social and political perspectives of the youth, as the city's population is primarily young, with roughly 60% of its population under 30 (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics, 2017) (Raza, 2020).

Young audiences in Lahore have become more engaged with influencers working in the fashion and lifestyle sectors. Exposure to both traditional Pakistani culture and international digital content has left the city's youth at a crossroads where their online consumption is constantly influencing their identity, goals, and self-perception (Raza, 2020). Fashion influencers frequently work with both domestic and foreign companies to promote goods that might not be within the means of all of their followers, which could lead to socioeconomic inequality. Additionally,

especially among impressionable teens and young adults, the carefully manicured and filtered lives that influencers display can lead to inflated expectations (Marwick, 2015).

This trend has been accelerated by the emergence of fashion bloggers and influencers. The way young people engage with brands, fashion trends, and ideals of body image is being transformed by fashion blogs and Instagram pages. These platforms provide an endless supply of aesthetically pleasing and frequently aspirational content that encourages particular consumer choices and lifestyles (Djafarova & Trofimenko, 2019). Such content can have both positive and negative effects in places like Lahore where traditional values coexist with contemporary digital influences. On the one hand, it encourages entrepreneurship, self-expression, and creativity. However, it can also reinforce materialistic lifestyles, unrealistic beauty standards, and mental health conditions like anxiety, low self-esteem, and body image dissatisfaction (Fardouly et al., 2015).

Social media and blogs have developed into vital marketing resources. Blogs were first used as digital diaries, like Links.net, which was established in 1994 (Rettberg, 2014). However, they have since evolved into powerful platforms for opinion formation, brand promotion, and content marketing. Large audiences can now be reached by fashion blogs and vlogs, which frequently have an impact comparable to that of traditional media. Fashion, beauty, food, travel, and lifestyle are just a few of the niches into which bloggers and influencers, including those on Instagram, fall. Each of these categories draws particular audiences and shapes their lifestyle choices and buying habits (Uzunoglu & Kip, 2014).

Furthermore, Instagram influencers now play a role that goes beyond just promoting purchases. Nowadays, a lot of people participate in cultural commentary, mental health awareness, and social activism, rising to prominence as opinion leaders in their online communities. Some may unintentionally reinforce negative stereotypes or promote unrealistic lifestyles, while others may advocate for inclusive and empowering content. Examining this phenomenon in particular cultural contexts, such as Lahore, where young people are quickly adjusting to a digital world while maintaining conservative social norms, is crucial

due to the duality of influence—both positive and negative (Khan et al., 2021).

The power that these Instagram celebrities have varies depending on the digital environment. Besides providing entertaining information about their personal lives, they serve as the place where young adults can present themselves, their ambitions and the important principles by exploring multiple niches—fashion, beauty, fitness, travel and even social activism (Marwick, 2015). Instagram influencers have developed beyond online celebrities by assuming a significant role in the lives of the youth by means of their well-selected content, sponsorships, and personal experiences. Besides being role models, they also serve as activists and opinion leaders, giving advice to the young people on all of their lifestyle choices to more general problems of society (Casal 2020; Djafarova & Trofimenko, 2019).

A wide variety of individuals can use the applications in the social media such as Instagram due to its ease and user-friendliness as well as its ease in downloading. They are essential instruments of digital communication and community development, since they offer such functions as messaging, interactive materials, and sharing of photos and videos (Pilkington et al., 2016). The risks of such accessibility, however, are the social comparison and availability of distorted depictions of life and cyberbullying that may have a negative effect on self-esteem and other psyche forms of an individual (Marwick, 2013).

On Instagram, users may subscribe to peers, influencers, and celebrities, and are exposed to the specifically pre-selected content regarding fashion, fitness, lifestyle, and beauty trends. Such celebrities often create unrealistic standards of achievement and beauty, and it may influence the self-perception of the girls and their bodies (Fardouly et al., 2015). The way the platform revolves around appearances and beauty has led to the increased usage of the editing tools and filters that alter the real physical appearance of the users, maintaining unrealistic beauty standards. As people feel overwhelmed with impeccable images (polished and even groomed), they may feel inadequate and anxious in relation to their image (Perloff, 2014). This is especially problematic in those cultures where social conformity and physical beauty is already at a premium.

What is more, the visual design of Instagram is more inclined toward the exterior look rather than the inner qualities that can only complicate the realization of their self-worth amongst the users, particularly those who are still in the process of identity formation—young women and adolescents especially. Research shows that body dissatisfaction and depressive signs are higher in those regularly exposed to the ideal images in Instagram (Tiggemann & Slater, 2014). The exposure to the negative consequences of social media is especially strong in young women due to the importance in many cultures including South Asian culture on valuing the traditional beauty ideals and social practices (Manago et al., 2008).

Irrespective of these challenges, Instagram remains a very popular platform. Its ability to create a feeling of connection, entertain people, and connect individuals in different parts of the globe makes it keep people interested. In association with reducing negative impacts of using social media, nothing is more important now than being able to be more critical in using the media and being more knowledgeable of mental health. The healthier social media requires education of its users, especially young women, on how to use it consciously and encourage diversity of body shapes and lifestyle presentation.

This research tries to determine the effect Instagram influencers have on the attitude, behaviour, lifestyle choices, and mental health of their followers among youth in Lahore. The research paper will consider practices in youth activity, the strategy of influencers in the content, cultural and psychological impact of following influencers. It aims at bridging the knowledge gap about how non-Western urban centres such as Lahore make the global digital trends their own, and reinterpret them.

The research will contribute to the broader debate on the role of digital media on the identities and behaviours of the youths by focusing on this dynamic population in the urban areas. It will also provide the teachers, parents, law-makers, and advertising agents with significant facts on how best to cope with the dangers and possibilities of the digital market. Through this, it intends to encourage in the Pakistani youth a more informed and rounded out way of engaging in the use of social media.

The importance of studying the role of Instagram influencers on young adults in the modern world is

hard to overestimate as the world is becoming more connected and the sphere of digital technology is covering more areas of everyday life. This study will unveil the intricacies of this relationship by throwing light on power dynamics, motivations and implications that define the relationship between the influencers and their followers in Lahore, Pakistan.

Theoretical Framework:

The Uses and Gratifications (U&G) Theory is a basic communication paradigm used to understand the spontaneous way in which individuals utilize the media to meet the specific needs and wants. U&G Theory is a theory designed in the middle of the 20th century by researchers such as Katz, Blumler, and Gurevitch. It is a revolutionary shift in the study of media since it puts a major stress on how the audience actively participates into consumption of the media instead of receiving messages delivered by the media in a passive way (Katz et al., 1973). This theory shows that individuals use the media in order to fulfill their various psychological and social needs through various ways of information gathering, entertainment, social contact, identity creation, and escaping reality (Rubin, 2009). The U&G theory is crucial with insight into different usages and interpretations of media by people, particularly in the current media environment where media is uniquely personal and undergoing digital conversion. U&G theory focuses on the role of the media audience in the selection and use of media content that conforms to their ability and personal preferences.

The U&G Theory of understanding the causes of young individuals engaging with these digital personalities is persuasive in examining the effects of Instagram influencers on young people in Lahore, Pakistan. As the studies say, young individuals are aware of Instagram influencers, who can relate to their values, interests, and needs (Jiang et al., 2021). As an example, often the influencers share the content, which is very influential to attract the attention of their audience by concentrating on a certain niche, such as fashion, beauty and lifestyle, fitness, or social activism. An adolescent living in Lahore could be a follower of lifestyle, lifestyle dude who lives values that he or she desires to learn or that of a fashion developer who models styles that he/she prefers. This selective involvement can be linked to the active audience

model developed by U&G Theory whereby individuals are not passive consumers but instead actively choose a media content that would meet their specific requirements (LaRose et al., 2001).

Moreover, U&G Theory focuses on the fact that one of the important elements of media consumption is social interaction with the environment and validation. This aspect is particularly relevant in the Instagram setting, where a plurality of young individuals interacts with influencers not just because of the content they produce but the community and a sense of belonging generated when they become a part of their following. As the researches show, social media communities are able to provide users with social approval and validation, which are valuable satisfying factors to many young individuals (Twitch, 2018). Having joined the community of known or influencing people, the youths have the capacity to find peers who share a similar passion, compare experiences and get the social approval they may feel as a result of this community feature. The comments, likes, and shares of these communities often create the sense of social belonging, which is in favour of the notion that Instagram influencers can shape the attitudes as well as social behaviours of their youthful followers based in Lahore.

The other key point, which U&G theory addresses, is identity formation that is highly relevant regarding the understanding of the impact on the young generation in Lahore by Instagram influencers. The most common type of influencers are aspirational people and the types of opinion, fashion, and lifestyle these people have are quite influential on the identity and self-concept of the people that follow them (Schau & Gilly, 2003). Being a follower of the influencer can be an example to the younger generation in Lahore to deal with the conundrum of identity due to the fast-forthcoming globalization of the world. This can cause severe changes in their self-perception and personal growth once they copy the attitude, behaviour, or fads of influencers and people who serve as a source of inspiration (Davis, 2018).

Information-seeking is also an essential characteristic not to be forgotten about as far as using the U&G Theory is concerned even counted in the influencers as a source of knowledge. To provide their followers with the information and advice that can help them, many influencers introduce themselves as experts in

their areas, be it social justice, fitness, or fashion (Harrison, 2020). The knowledge base and opinions of the youth about Lahore can be proved greatly affected by the presence of Instagram influencers, who can give them easy access to sets of information on trends, health and even political or social issues.

Last but not least, as U&G Theory suggests, the reason that young people are attracted to the Instagram influencers is because they need to be amused and addicted to escape their reality. Whether it be entertaining messages, exciting stories, or attractive pictures, influencers often publish some interesting content that allows people to breathe out of routine life patterns (Sundar & Limperos, 2013). This entertainment factor can become the key drive of young owners of Lahore to subscribe to specific figures and bring them some pleasure and relief of their everyday life.

The aim of the study is to establish the underlying reasons that make young people engage with influencers using U&G Theory to examine the impacts of Instagram influencers on the youths in Lahore. It is also directed toward the revelation of the way, by means of the specific sociocultural skin of Lahore, these shapers shape the identity, preferences, and behaviour of their admirers. This technique will provide a deep understanding of how digital technology has influenced the current youth culture in Pakistan.

Methodology:**Population of the Study:**

The population of the study is the students from private universities of Lahore, Pakistan. The group is particularly relevant because of their use of social media sites more regularly such as Instagram and also because they are vulnerable to being persuaded by the online trendsetters. As the individuals in this age category have diverse interests and their backgrounds, this target population is the best sample to examine the influence of Instagram influencers on their lives in various aspects.

Sampling Technique:

A probability sampling method, more specifically simple random sampling, is used to obtain sampling data about this population. This technique decreases bias because by ensuring that all the members of the

population get an equal probability of selection, it increases the representativeness of the sample. As the study targets students of the private universities of Lahore random sampling is conducted, where random numbers with the outcomes that correspond to students' IDs of individuals in the population are generated. This makes sure that no systematic exclusion occurs with regards to the participants. The approach is chosen because of its simplicity and effectiveness of ensuring fair representation of the people, in the constraints of accessibility and time.

Sample Size:

308 male and female students from Lahore private universities make up the study's sample size. This sample size is determined based on the following considerations:

Statistical Significance: A sample of 308 provides a reasonable balance between reliability and manageability, allowing for robust statistical analysis while remaining feasible for data collection within the limited timeframe of the study.

Data Collection:

Data is collected using a structured survey questionnaire. The questionnaire is distributed electronically via a Google Form to the selected sample population. The survey consists predominantly of closed-ended questions to facilitate the collection of quantitative data. In addition, several sub-questions are crafted under the main research questions to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the various aspects of influencer impact being studied.

Data Analysis:

The collected data is analysed using descriptive statistics. The data is entered into SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) software for analysis. The results are summarized and presented in tables and graphs to provide a clear and visual representation of the findings, allowing for easier interpretation and comparison of responses.

Ethical Considerations:

The study strictly adheres to ethical principles, including informed consent, confidentiality, and anonymity. Participants are informed about the

purpose of the study, their rights as participants, and the voluntary nature of their participation. Measures are taken to ensure that the data collected remains confidential and that individual responses are anonymized to protect the privacy of all participants.

Limitation of Study:

This study is limited in many ways. It relies solely on surveys as a method of collecting data, and this is not one that may bind the most diverse, unique experiences participants may have. In addition, the sample comprises only students of a single private university in Lahore, which restricts the scope of findings to the other region or population. Response bias is another danger of using self-reported data due to the reason that participants might provide socially acceptable responses. Moreover, this study cannot even draw any causal relations since the data is gathered at one time period. Future research studies can thwart these limitations through the inclusion of interviews, the expansion of the sample of participants including those with diverse backgrounds, and the longitudinal design which allows a more profound comprehension of the aspects of the research.

Study Variables:

This study identifies two fundamental types of variables as follows:

Dependent Variable:

The dependent variable of the study is called as youth in Lahore. This variable that is influenced by additional factors that have been discussed in the study is the main point of interest in the study.

Independent Variable:

The independent variable that is considered in this study is referred to as the Instagram influencers. The impact of this variable falls on the dependent variable, the youths in Lahore, and these are investigated.

Results:

This chapter presents the result of the study that aimed to establish the influence of Instagram influencers on the youths in Lahore. Discussing the impacts of these influencers on the different aspects of the life of young people, including their behaviour, lifestyle, and decision-making, was the principal aim. Data were collected in a form of a questionnaire that was administered to male and female respondents of all ages and backgrounds. This made the research learn through diversity of ideas and experiences.

To establish the reaction of people of different type to the messages left by Instagram influencers through demographic data of the respondents were collected in the analysis. In so doing, the study will be able to identify tendencies and differences in the manner in which young people get influenced basing on their backgrounds. The results indicate the way that social media is propagating more and more on the minds and behaviour of younger citizens.

Table 1
Participant Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	105	34.1	34.1	34.1
	Female	203	65.9	65.9	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: 65.9% of the participants were female and 34.1% were male, indicating a higher female representation in the study.

Table 2
Participant Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Zq21`	18-24	195	63.3	63.3	63.3
	25-34	105	34.1	34.1	97.4
	35-44	4	1.3	1.3	98.7
	45 and above	4	1.3	1.3	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: The majority of participants (63.3%) were aged 18–24, followed by 34.1% aged 25–34. This indicates that most respondents were young adults.

Interpretation: The majority of the participants were graduates (73.7%). Some had an intermediate level of education (8.8%), and a few were matriculates (2.6%) or postgraduates (14.9%).

Table 4
Participant economic class

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Upper Class (At over PKR 150,000 monthly)	106	34.4	34.4	34.4
	Upper-Middle Class (Approximately PKR 80,000 to 150,000 monthly)	117	38.0	38.0	72.4
	Lower-Middle Class (Between PKR 40,000 to 80,000 monthly)	65	21.1	21.1	93.5
	Lower Class (Below PKR 40,000 monthly)	20	6.5	6.5	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: The majority of participants belonged to the upper-middle class (38.0%), followed by the upper class (34.4%). Some were from the lower-middle class (21.1%), while a smaller portion came from the lower class (6.5%).

Table 5
I often follow fashion trends promoted by Instagram influencers.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	27	8.8	8.8	8.8
	Disagree	35	11.4	11.4	20.1
	Neutral	136	44.2	44.2	64.3
	Agree	87	28.2	28.2	92.5
	Strongly Agree	23	7.5	7.5	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

I often follow fashion trends promoted by Instagram influencers.

Interpretation: A total of 8.8% of participants strongly disagreed and 11.4% disagreed with following fashion trends promoted by Instagram influencers. The largest group, 44.2%, remained neutral. Meanwhile, 28.2% agreed and 7.5% strongly agreed.

Instagram influencers inspire my personal style and clothing choices.

Table 6
Instagram influencers inspire my personal style and clothing choices.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	24	7.8	7.8	7.8
	Disagree	59	19.2	19.2	26.9
	Neutral	125	40.6	40.6	67.5
	Agree	79	25.6	25.6	93.2
	Strongly Agree	21	6.8	6.8	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: 7.8% of participants strongly disagreed and 19.2% disagreed that Instagram influencers inspire their personal style and clothing choices. The largest group, 40.6%, remained neutral. Meanwhile, 25.6% agreed and 6.8% strongly agreed.

Table 7
I try new fashion or lifestyle habits after seeing them on Instagram.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	17	5.5	5.5	5.5
	Disagree	62	20.1	20.1	25.6
	Neutral	94	30.5	30.5	56.2
	Agree	116	37.7	37.7	93.8
	Strongly Agree	19	6.2	6.2	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: 5.5% of participants strongly disagreed and 20.1% disagreed that they try new fashion or lifestyle habits after seeing them on Instagram. About 30.5% remained neutral. Meanwhile, 37.7% agreed and 6.2% strongly agreed.

Table 8
My daily lifestyle (e.g., routines, hobbies) is influenced by Instagram influencers.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	58	18.8	18.8	18.8
	Disagree	105	34.1	34.1	52.9
	Neutral	89	28.9	28.9	81.8
	Agree	44	14.3	14.3	96.1
	Strongly Agree	12	3.9	3.9	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: 18.8% of participants strongly disagreed and 34.1% disagreed that their daily lifestyle is influenced by Instagram influencers. Around 28.9% remained neutral, while 14.3% agreed and 3.9% strongly agreed

Table 9
I consider Instagram influencers to be role models for fashion and lifestyle.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	70	22.7	22.7	22.7
	Disagree	91	29.5	29.5	52.3
	Neutral	76	24.7	24.7	76.9
	Agree	60	19.5	19.5	96.4
	Strongly Agree	11	3.6	3.6	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: 22.7% of participants strongly disagreed and 29.5% disagreed with considering Instagram influencers as role models for fashion and lifestyle. About 24.7% remained neutral, while 19.5% agreed and 3.6% strongly agreed.

Table 10
I spend more on fashion or lifestyle products because of what I see on Instagram.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	62	20.1	20.1	20.1
	Disagree	87	28.2	28.2	48.4
	Neutral	73	23.7	23.7	72.1
	Agree	69	22.4	22.4	94.5
	Strongly Agree	17	5.5	5.5	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Table 11
I compare my appearance to Instagram influencers.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	79	25.6	25.6	25.6
	Disagree	105	34.1	34.1	59.7
	Neutral	80	26.0	26.0	85.7
	Agree	38	12.3	12.3	98.1
	Strongly Agree	6	1.9	1.9	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: 20.1% of participants strongly disagreed and 28.2% disagreed that they spend more on fashion or lifestyle products because of what they see on Instagram. About 23.7% remained neutral, while 22.4% agreed and 5.5% strongly agreed.

Interpretation: 25.6% of participants strongly disagreed and 34.1% disagreed that they compare their appearance to Instagram influencers. About 26.0% remained neutral, while 12.3% agreed and 1.9% strongly agreed.

Table 12
I feel pressure to look a certain way because of Instagram influencers.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	72	23.4	23.4	23.4
	Disagree	112	36.4	36.4	59.7
	Neutral	63	20.5	20.5	80.2
	Agree	53	17.2	17.2	97.4
	Strongly Agree	8	2.6	2.6	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: 23.4% of participants strongly disagreed and 36.4% disagreed that they feel pressure to look a certain way because of Instagram influencers. About 20.5% remained neutral, while 17.2% agreed and 2.6% strongly agreed.

Table 13
Following influencers sometimes makes me feel less confident about my body.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	67	21.8	21.8	21.8
	Disagree	79	25.6	25.6	47.4
	Neutral	74	24.0	24.0	71.4
	Agree	67	21.8	21.8	93.2
	Strongly Agree	21	6.8	6.8	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: 21.8% of participants strongly disagreed and 25.6% disagreed that following influencers makes them feel less confident about their body. About 24.0% remained neutral, while 21.8% agreed and 6.8% strongly agreed.

Table 14
Instagram influencers make me more conscious about my body image.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	56	18.2	18.2	18.2
	Disagree	81	26.3	26.3	44.5
	Neutral	75	24.4	24.4	68.8
	Agree	76	24.7	24.7	93.5
	Strongly Agree	20	6.5	6.5	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: 18.2% of participants strongly disagreed and 26.3% disagreed that Instagram influencers make them more conscious about their body image. About 24.4% remained neutral, while 24.7% agreed and 6.5% strongly agreed.

Table 15
My self-esteem is affected by how I compare myself to people on Instagram.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	59	19.2	19.2	19.2
	Disagree	97	31.5	31.5	50.6
	Neutral	73	23.7	23.7	74.4
	Agree	69	22.4	22.4	96.8
	Strongly Agree	10	3.2	3.2	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: 19.2% of participants strongly disagreed and 31.5% disagreed that their self-esteem is affected by comparing themselves to people on Instagram. About 23.7% remained neutral, while 22.4% agreed and 3.2% strongly agreed.

Table 16
I feel motivated to improve myself physically after seeing influencers' posts.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	22	7.1	7.1	7.1

Disagree	47	15.3	15.3	22.4
Neutral	111	36.0	36.0	58.4
Agree	106	34.4	34.4	92.9
Strongly Agree	22	7.1	7.1	100.0
Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: 7.1% of participants strongly disagreed and 15.3% disagreed that they feel motivated to improve themselves physically after seeing influencers’ posts. About 36.0% remained neutral, while 34.4% agreed and 7.1% strongly agreed.

Table 17: I have purchased products promoted by Instagram influencers.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	40	13.0	13.0	13.0
	Disagree	55	17.9	17.9	30.8
	Neutral	86	27.9	27.9	58.8
	Agree	107	34.7	34.7	93.5
	Strongly Agree	20	6.5	6.5	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: 13.0% of participants strongly disagreed and 17.9% disagreed that they have purchased products promoted by Instagram influencers. About 27.9% remained neutral, while 34.7% agreed and 6.5% strongly agreed.

Table 18
I trust the product recommendations of Instagram influencers.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	52	16.9	16.9	16.9
	Disagree	50	16.2	16.2	33.1
	Neutral	94	30.5	30.5	63.6
	Agree	95	30.8	30.8	94.5
	Strongly Agree	17	5.5	5.5	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Table 19
I am likely to try a new product if an influencer I follow recommends it.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	45	14.6	14.6	14.6
	Disagree	51	16.6	16.6	31.2
	Neutral	87	28.2	28.2	59.4
	Agree	111	36.0	36.0	95.5
	Strongly Agree	14	4.5	4.5	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: 16.9% of participants strongly disagreed, and 16.2% disagreed. About 30.5% remained neutral, while 30.8% agreed, and 5.5% strongly agreed.

Table 20
Influencers affect my decisions about which brands or services to choose.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	42	13.6	13.6	13.6
	Disagree	76	24.7	24.7	38.3
	Neutral	102	33.1	33.1	71.4
	Agree	75	24.4	24.4	95.8
	Strongly Agree	13	4.2	4.2	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: 16.9% of participants strongly disagreed, and 16.2% disagreed. About 30.5% remained neutral, while 30.8% agreed, and 5.5% strongly agreed.

Interpretation: 13.6% of respondents strongly disagreed and 24.7% disagreed. Around 33.1% were neutral, while 24.4% agreed and 4.2% strongly agreed.

Interpretation: 16.2% strongly disagreed and 26.0% disagreed. About one-third (33.8%) were neutral, while 21.1% agreed and 2.9% strongly agreed.

Table 21
Instagram influencer promotions have changed the way I shop or spend money.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	50	16.2	16.2	16.2
	Disagree	80	26.0	26.0	42.2
	Neutral	104	33.8	33.8	76.0
	Agree	65	21.1	21.1	97.1
	Strongly Agree	9	2.9	2.9	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Table 22
I believe the influencers I follow provide honest opinions about products.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	37	12.0	12.0	12.0
	Disagree	68	22.1	22.1	34.1
	Neutral	131	42.5	42.5	76.6
	Agree	65	21.1	21.1	97.7
	Strongly Agree	7	2.3	2.3	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Table 23

I consider influencers trustworthy when they disclose sponsored content.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	40	13.0	13.0	13.0
	Disagree	56	18.2	18.2	31.2
	Neutral	109	35.4	35.4	66.6
	Agree	92	29.9	29.9	96.4
	Strongly Agree	11	3.6	3.6	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: 12.0% of participants strongly disagreed and 22.1% disagreed that influencers provide honest opinions about products. Meanwhile, 42.5% remained neutral, and 21.1% agreed with 2.3% strongly agreeing.

Interpretation: 13.0% of participants strongly disagreed and 18.2% disagreed that they consider influencers trustworthy when they disclose sponsored content. About 35.4% remained neutral, while 29.9% agreed and 3.6% strongly agreed.

Table 24

I am more likely to trust influencers who frequently engage with their followers.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	16	5.2	5.2	5.2
	Disagree	68	22.1	22.1	27.3
	Neutral	108	35.1	35.1	62.3
	Agree	107	34.7	34.7	97.1
	Strongly Agree	9	2.9	2.9	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: A total of 5.2% of participants strongly disagreed and 22.1% disagreed that they are more likely to trust influencers who frequently engage with their followers. About 35.1% remained neutral, while 34.7% agreed and 2.9% strongly agreed.

Table 25
I trust influencers who share personal experiences over paid promotions.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	12	3.9	3.9	3.9
	Disagree	34	11.0	11.0	14.9
	Neutral	113	36.7	36.7	51.6
	Agree	115	37.3	37.3	89.0
	Strongly Agree	34	11.0	11.0	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: 3.9% of participants strongly disagreed and 11.0% disagreed that they trust influencers who share personal experiences over paid promotions. About 36.7% remained neutral, while 37.3% agreed and 11.0% strongly agreed

Table 26
I prefer following influencers who seem authentic and reliable.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	13	4.2	4.2	4.2
	Disagree	23	7.5	7.5	11.7
	Neutral	92	29.9	29.9	41.6
	Agree	146	47.4	47.4	89.0
	Strongly Agree	34	11.0	11.0	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Table 27
My level of trust affects how much I engage with an influencer’s content.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	21	6.8	6.8	6.8
	Disagree	46	14.9	14.9	21.8
	Neutral	131	42.5	42.5	64.3
	Agree	97	31.5	31.5	95.8
	Strongly Agree	13	4.2	4.2	100.0
	Total	308	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: 4.2% of participants strongly disagreed and 7.5% disagreed that they prefer following influencers who seem authentic and reliable. About 29.9% remained neutral, while 47.4% agreed and 11.0% strongly agreed.

Interpretation: 6.8% of participants strongly disagreed and 14.9% disagreed that their level of trust affects how much they engage with an influencer’s content. About 42.5% remained neutral, while 31.5% agreed and 4.2% strongly agreed.

Discussion:

This study aimed to explore the multifaceted impact of Instagram influencers on youth in Lahore, focusing on their behaviour, lifestyle, consumer patterns, and psychological well-being. The findings reveal a complex interplay of influence, with Instagram acting as both a source of inspiration and pressure for young individuals navigating their identities in a rapidly digitizing world.

Demographic Insights and Their Relevance

The predominance of female respondents (65.9%) in the sample aligns with existing literature suggesting that women engage more intensively with Instagram content, especially in categories such as fashion, beauty, and lifestyle (Casaló, Flavián & Ibáñez-Sánchez, 2018). The age concentration in the 18-24 bracket (63.3%) also reflects global trends where young adults represent the core Instagram demographic, given their high digital literacy and social media dependency.

Participants' high levels of education and socioeconomic standing (primarily upper-middle and upper classes) imply that these groups have more access to technology and disposable income, which probably increases how they engage with influencer content. This socioeconomic component is important because it allows young people to afford and aspire to

the lifestyles that influencers advocate, which may encourage consumerism and status-signalling.

Influence on Fashion, Lifestyle, and Consumer Choices

The conflicting answers about adopting lifestyle and fashion trends point to a complex interaction between young people and influencers. A larger portion is neutral or disagrees, suggesting selective acceptance rather than mass imitation, even though nearly one-third actively adopt new trends they see on Instagram. This finding might suggest that young people are becoming more media literate and sceptical, as they become aware of the profit-driven nature of influencer content. It also illustrates how influencers play a dual role as both commercial agents and aspirational figures, which makes it more difficult for young people to interact with such content. Influencers may inspire young people, but they still have some control over what they choose to embrace.

Interestingly, a sizable percentage of participants acknowledged that influencer content had led to higher spending on lifestyle or fashion items. This supports earlier studies showing that influencer marketing can influence young consumers' purchase intentions and actual purchasing behaviour (Lou & Yuan, 2019). These results highlight the significance of ethical marketing strategies as well as the economic

power of influencers in influencing consumer behaviour.

Psychological and Emotional Impact

The Instagram influencers appear to positively and negatively psychologically impact youth. On the one hand, many participants reported that the views of the posts of their influencers motivated them to improve their physical health or their physical appearance, and this could stimulate positive self-care behaviours.

Nevertheless, a considerable number also experienced comparison-based unhappiness, low body image, and notion to conform to specific beauty ideals. The two effects resemble the so-called highlight reel effect that occurs on social media when people form negative self-assessment and have impossible expectations by comparing their lives with photographs of influencers carefully selected to present only the best of the best (Fardouly et al., 2015).

This category has a lot of neutral responses and it can be an indicator of ambivalence or even a coping mechanism of young people to reach a compromise of appreciation and awareness of the fakery of influencer content. It could also mean that the harmful consequences vary significantly depending on their personal traits such as media literacy, social support and self-worth.

Trust, Authenticity, and Engagement with Influencers

One important factor affecting how young people engage with influencer content is trust. In contrast to influencers who only post promotional content, respondents indicated that they preferred influencers who reveal sponsorships, interact frequently with their followers, and share relatable, personal experiences.

This preference lends credence to the idea of "parasocial relationships," in which followers identify personally with influencers who are seen as genuine and reliable (Horton & Wohl, 1956). Therefore, authenticity is a great asset for influencers because it influences followers' acceptance of their recommendations and opinions in addition to increasing engagement.

However, the comparatively high neutral position on sponsored content disclosure and influencer honesty points to some scepticism among young people,

possibly as a result of growing awareness of influencer marketing strategies. This ambivalence emphasizes how influencer marketing must adhere to ethical and transparent standards in order to remain credible.

Role of Instagram Influencers in Youth Culture and Identity Formation

Instagram influencers play a significant role in youth culture as social agents by providing fresh role models for aspirations related to identity, appearance, and lifestyle. In order to achieve social acceptance and self-affirmation, young people may try to integrate the symbolic capital they provide into their own identities.

However, the study shows that young people do not passively absorb messages from influencers. Young people actively interpret, negotiate, and occasionally reject influencer content based on their values, experiences, and critical thinking, as evidenced by the high percentage of neutral responses across numerous influence-related statements.

A more sophisticated comprehension of the constructed nature of social media and an increase in digital media literacy may be associated with this critical engagement. Additionally, it indicates a changing youth culture that both accepts and challenges the influence of online influencers.

Societal and Cultural Implications

Instagram Influencers represent carriers of global trends and expose not only Pakistani youth to Western fashion, beauty ideals and consumer culture in the city of Lahore, where alongside traditional values, modern values prevail. Modernity versus cultural norms can influence the gender roles, the body image ideals and patterns of consumption.

The effect of Instagram can undermine the social norms as it allows young individuals, especially females, to be more confident and unique to explore a new style and image. Nevertheless, it has the potential to enforce consumerism and the idea of unattainable beauty, contributing to mental issues and financial pressure.

Therefore, these findings underscore the importance of culturally sensitive media literacy initiatives that address both the opportunities and risks associated with influencer culture, helping youth navigate social media responsibly.

Limitations and Recommendations for Future Research

While this study provides valuable insights, its limitations must be acknowledged. The predominance of female and upper-class respondents may limit the generalizability of the findings across all youth in Lahore, especially males and lower socioeconomic groups who might engage differently with influencers.

Additionally, the cross-sectional design captures a snapshot in time, without addressing how influencer impact evolves longitudinally. Future research could adopt mixed-method approaches to explore qualitative nuances and causal relationships over time.

Further research could also examine the role of gender, as male youth may experience and respond to influencer culture in different ways, potentially emphasizing different types of influencers (e.g., sports, technology). Moreover, exploring the impact of influencers on youth from rural or lower socioeconomic backgrounds would provide a more comprehensive understanding.

Practical Implications

The findings have practical implications for educators, policymakers, mental health professionals, and marketers. There is a clear need to integrate social media literacy programs in educational curricula, helping youth critically assess influencer content, understand commercial motives, and manage psychological impacts.

Mental health practitioners should be aware of the pressures arising from social media comparisons and provide supportive interventions to mitigate negative effects on body image and self-esteem.

Marketers and influencers themselves bear responsibility to maintain ethical standards, ensuring transparency in advertising, promoting diverse and realistic images, and engaging followers authentically.

Conclusion

This study offers a thorough grasp of the ways in which Instagram influencers impact Lahore's youth in a number of areas, including behaviour, lifestyle, shopping patterns, and self-perception. According to the data, Instagram influencers are very prevalent in young people's daily lives, particularly among females

and young adults (ages 18 to 24), who make up the majority of the sample.

The results show that although a sizable percentage of young people have no opinion about the influence of Instagram celebrities, a significant portion actively adopts the fashions, trends, and lifestyles that these influencers advocate. This demonstrates that influencers are significant role models who affect young people's fashion preferences, lifestyle choices, and purchasing habits in Lahore.

Another interesting finding related to the study is high level of scepticism and critical awareness among the youth. The number of contradictions and neutral answers when it comes to following blindly leads to the trends is high, which suggests some conscious interaction with the works of influencers instead of blind adoration. This is where the subtlety of influence is key to recognizing that it is not black and white but instead is by way of individual attitudes and values.

The psychological aspect of influence of Instagram influencers on the younger generation is complicated and has many dimensions. Different people report being motivated to transform their lifestyle and physical image, some negative effects, such as the problem with the body image, self-esteem, and being pressure to conform to the unrealistic beauty ideals. The findings demonstrate that social media power is capable of motivating, as well as problematic to the psychological self-being of the youth, and therefore compassionate effort is required to address the situation.

Trust is one significant factor that determines the interaction of the youth with influencers. The participants will trust those influencers who appear real, easy-going, and open about sponsored content. This implies that to win the trust and influence in life, influencers need to be real and ethical participants in real engagement activities.

To conclude it all, this paper will provide insight into the growing role of Instagram influencers as the cultural shapers defining the identity, consumption, and social behaviour of the Lahore youth. The results indicate that the effect of the influencers can be both constructive and inspirational on the one hand, yet quite dangerous on the other hand in terms of the risks connected with consumerism and mental health issues.

These insights propose a multipronged approach combined of mental health support, professional marketing of influencers, and teaching digital literacy to help young people experience the effects of social media influence in a more conscious and healthy manner. Future studies that extend the analysis to other cities, platforms, and other populations will help in better understanding of the transforming impact of social media in the youth culture.

REFERENCES

- Abidin, C. (2016). Affective publics and popular social media influencers in Southeast Asia. *Media International Australia*, 160(1), 91–103. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1329878X16642063>
- Abidin, C. (2016). Influencer marketing: The impacts of social media influencers on consumer behavior. *Journal of Business Research*, 120, 153–160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.04.001>
- Alalwan, A. A., & Rana, N. P. (2017). Social media influencers and their role in changing youth consumption behavior. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 36, 317–323. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2017.01.002>
- Arif, F., & Hayat, Z. (2017). Impact of social media on youth: A case study of Lahore. *Lahore Journal of Policy Studies*, 4(2), 45–58.
- boyd, d., & Ellison, N. B. (2007). Social network sites: Definition, history, and scholarship. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 13(1), 210–230. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1083-6101.2007.00393.x>
- Casaló, L. V., Flavián, C., & Guinaliú, M. (2020). Influencers on Instagram: The role of the source in consumer engagement. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, 26(7), 648–666. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13527266.2018.1472185>
- Casaló, L. V., Flavián, C., & Ibáñez-Sánchez, S. (2018). Influencers on Instagram: Antecedents and consequences of opinion leadership. *Journal of Business Research*, 117, 510–519. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2018.07.005>
- Castells, M. (2012). *Communication power*. Oxford University Press.
- Chaudhary, R., & Sharma, P. (2021). Instagram and youth: The new trendsetters. *International Journal of Social Media Studies*, 8(4), 245–258. <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJSMS.2021040102>
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (4th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Davis, K. (2018). The impact of social media influencers on young consumers' identity formation. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 45(5), 1234–1249. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jcr/ucy012>
- Djafarova, E., & Trofimenko, O. (2019). Exploring the relationship between influencer marketing and consumer behavior. *International Journal of Advertising*, 38(6), 919–944. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02650487.2019.1621730>
- Fardouly, J., Diedrichs, P. C., Vartanian, L. R., & Halliwell, E. (2015). Social comparisons on social media: The impact of Facebook on young women's body image concerns and mood. *Body Image*, 13, 38–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bodyim.2014.12.003>
- Fardouly, J., & Vartanian, L. R. (2018). Social media and body image concerns: Current research and future directions. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 19, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsy.2017.11.002>
- Freberg, K., Graham, K., McGaughey, K., & Freberg, L. A. (2011). Who are the social media influencers? A study of public perceptions of personality. *Public Relations Review*, 37(1), 90–92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pubrev.2010.11.001>
- Haenlein, M., & Libai, B. (2013). Targeting influential customers as a marketing strategy. *California Management Review*, 55(4), 91–107. <https://doi.org/10.1525/cm.2013.55.4.91>
- Harrison, K. (2020). Influencers as sources of information: How followers engage with digital content. *Journal of Digital Marketing*, 12(2), 67–81.

- Horton, D., & Wohl, R. R. (1956). Mass communication and para-social interaction: Observations on intimacy at a distance. *Psychiatry*, 19(3), 215-229. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00332747.1956.11023049>
- Iqbal, Z., & Lodhi, A. (2019). Influence of social media on youth in Pakistan: A study on fashion consumption. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences*, 39(2), 101-118.
- Jiang, Y., Liu, Y., Wang, J., & Lu, Y. (2021). The relationship between social media influencers and follower engagement: A Uses and Gratifications approach. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 37(5-6), 509-528. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0267257X.2021.1919002>
- Katz, E., Blumler, J. G., & Gurevitch, M. (1973). Uses and gratifications research. *Public Opinion Quarterly*, 37(4), 509-523. <https://doi.org/10.1086/268109>
- Khan, A. R., Ali, R., & Asim, M. (2021). The impact of social media influencers on youth in Pakistan: A study of Instagram influencers. *Journal of Youth Studies*, 24(7), 877-893. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13676261.2021.1892185>
- Khan, S., & Akhtar, N. (2020). Digital influence: How social media influencers affect youth in South Asia. *Asian Journal of Communication*, 30(3), 276-292. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01292986.2020.1742541>
- LaRose, R., Mastro, D., & Eastin, M. S. (2001). The impact of internet communication on social interaction: The Uses and Gratifications perspective. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1083-6101.2001.tb00114.x>
- Lee, H. J., & Eastin, M. S. (2020). The impact of social media influencers on adolescents' body image. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, 23(7), 443-449. <https://doi.org/10.1089/cyber.2019.0367>
- Marwick, A. E. (2015). Instafame: Luxury selfies in the attention economy. *Public Culture*, 27(1), 137-160. <https://doi.org/10.1215/08992363-2797740>
- Pakistan Bureau of Statistics. (2017). Population and housing census 2017. Government of Pakistan. <https://www.pbs.gov.pk/content/population-and-housing-census-2017>
- Rubin, A. M. (2009). Uses and gratifications: The uses and gratifications perspective. In P. J. Kalbfleisch (Ed.), *Communication and technology: A guide for the 21st century* (pp. 3-22). Routledge.
- Schau, H. J., & Gilly, M. C. (2003). We are what we post? Self-presentation in personal weblogs. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 30(3), 385-404. <https://doi.org/10.1086/378616>
- Sundar, S. S., & Limperos, A. M. (2013). Uses and grats 2.0: New gratifications for new media. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 29(3), 502-510. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2012.10.006>
- Twitch, M. (2018). Social media validation: Understanding the influence of influencers on youth behaviors. *Youth & Society*, 50(6), 823-842. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0044118X16646019>
- Lou, C., & Yuan, S. (2019). Influencer marketing: How message value and credibility affect consumer trust of branded content on social media. *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 19(1), 58-73. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15252019.2018.1533501>